

4.	B ₆ (pyridoxine)	11,657	37,2
5.	B ₉ (folic acid)	14,046	42,4
6.	B ₂ (riboflavin)	15,012	39,4

The Content of Water-Soluble Vitamins in the Aerial Part of *Trifolium repens* L.

Conclusions: HPLC analysis of the aerial part of *Trifolium repens* L. identified ascorbic acid (vitamin C) as the predominant water-soluble vitamin, supporting the plant's chemical characterization.